

COMBINING NON-INTRUSIVE AND EXTRACTIVE METHODOLOGIES FOR SOOT DETERMINATION ON AIRCRAFT ENGINE EMISSIONS

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Associated conference topics: 2.5

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The incomplete combustion of fuel Jet-A1 produces soot particles which are then emitted in aircraft engine exhaust. Soot consists of a carbonaceous core, Elemental Carbon (EC), with adsorbed volatile organic species, Organic Carbon (OC) condensing under cooler than exhaust conditions. Black Carbon (BC) consists of the light absorbing fraction of the carbonaceous aerosols which can be considered equivalent to EC. Estimation of the BC/OC ratio is critical as climate models recognise the Global Warming Potential (GWP) of BC as the second most important climate forcing agent after carbon dioxide (Bond, 2013). Emissions generated by commercial aircraft are facing increasingly stringent environmental regulations in the EU and U.S. (ICAO, 2017). Currently there is limited understanding of aircraft emissions associated with engine operation in and around airports, especially in respect of ultrafine particles (PM_{0.1}). This is due to the difficulty of measuring aircraft emissions during normal ground operations, using sampling locations that may be far from the active taxiway or runway. In some cases, it is hard to isolate the source contributions of individual aircraft plumes, leading to inconsistent understanding of data. Therefore, there is a need for more research to fully understand particle emissions and plume growth methods.

As a national research institution, INTA is supporting European and the Rolls-Royce initiatives to achieve the environmental goals of the European vision for aviation (Flightpath 2050). Research into non-volatile particulate matter (nvPM/soot) emissions under dynamic engine operating conditions that influence soot formation requires the development of novel sampling techniques. INTA has therefore taken part in two European programmes (*Service provision towards the development of a Public European Environmental Model Suite for Aviation* and the Clean Sky initiative CIDAR: *Combustion species Imaging Diagnostics for Aero-engine Research*). These programmes have provided enhanced exhaust plane soot quantification capability, including the Emission Traverse Probe (ETP), an extractive sampling measurement system (Fig. 1(left and centre)), and non-intrusive cross-sectional imaging of nvPM (Figure 1, right), based on Laser Induced Incandescence, demonstrated at INTA's jet engine test facility.

Figure 1. Soot measurement non-intrusive technique (left), Emission Traverse Probe (centre), block diagram for nvPM/soot determination with extractive measurement system (right).

Although non-intrusive techniques have some advantages, especially in dynamic situations, they do not as yet offer a full aerosol property measurement solution. Exploring and predicting particle growth dynamics requires a comprehensive understanding of not only the soot mass concentration distribution across the exhaust but also the corresponding, spatially-resolved, particle size distribution. These are also needed when investigating the chemical properties of the engine exhaust and in modelling plume evolution. Until non-intrusive techniques are able to provide independent *in-situ* measurement of particle size distribution, with the required resolution and size range, their combination with extractive techniques is likely to provide the most complete solution for soot emission determination.

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 785539.

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